

GRPO-RAD: GROUP RELATIVE POLICY OPTIMIZATION FOR RADIOLOGY REPORT SUMMARIZATION

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ABSTRACT

We investigate Group Relative Policy Optimization (GRPO) for radiology report summarization using Qwen 3.0 models. GRPO enables optimization of composite reward functions combining syntactic and semantic measures, addressing limitations of traditional supervised fine-tuning. Our comprehensive evaluation on MIMIC-III demonstrates that GRPO consistently outperforms baseline and supervised fine-tuning approaches across multiple metrics including ROUGE-L and F1-RadGraph.

1 INTRODUCTION

Radiology reports comprise detailed findings sections that present comprehensive examination results and impression sections that provide concise summaries of key clinical insights for decision-making. Manual summarization is labour-intensive and inconsistent, motivating automated approaches. Traditional supervised fine-tuning optimizes for token-level prediction accuracy, often failing to capture nuanced clinical quality aspects. GRPO enables fine-grained control over training objectives by combining quantitative reward functions with customizable weightings, incorporating both syntactic and semantic measures.

We investigate GRPO for radiology report summarization using Qwen 3.0 decoder-only transformers. Our evaluation demonstrates that GRPO consistently outperforms baseline models and supervised fine-tuning across multiple metrics, achieving substantial improvements in syntactic similarity and clinical factual correctness. This represents the first application of GRPO to radiology report summarization.¹

2 RELATED WORK

Decoder-only transformer architectures have demonstrated effectiveness for text generation through flexible prompting strategies (Brown et al., 2020), while prior medical text summarization approaches using encoder-decoder architectures (Zhang et al., 2020b) rely on supervised learning objectives that optimize for token-level prediction accuracy, potentially missing nuanced clinical quality aspects.

Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) addresses alignment between model outputs and human preferences (Ouyang et al., 2022), showing superior generalization compared to supervised fine-tuning (Kirk et al., 2023). However, RLHF faces challenges including training instability, reward design complexity, and computational costs (Zheng et al., 2023). Shao et al. (2024) introduced GRPO as an advancement over RLHF, enabling fine-grained control over training objectives by combining quantitative reward functions with customizable weightings.

Parameter-efficient fine-tuning through LoRA (Hu et al., 2022) enables performance improvements while tuning minimal parameters. Van Veen et al. (2023) demonstrated effective radiology summarization using only 0.32% of model parameters. Prior radiology work focuses on encoder-decoder

¹Code and data are available at: https://github.com/FargolN/grpo_rad

Figure 1: Experimental methodology varying prompting strategies, few-shot configurations, model architectures, and fine-tuning approaches, yielding 24 configurations.

architectures (Johnson et al., 2019) with syntactic metrics that inadequately capture clinical relevance (Zhang et al., 2020b).

Our work represents the first application of GRPO to radiology report summarization, combining LoRA fine-tuning with optimization for both syntactic and semantic metrics.

3 METHODS

We investigate radiology report summarization using decoder-only transformer models with GRPO (Shao et al., 2024), comparing effectiveness against base models and traditional supervised fine-tuning across different model sizes, prompting strategies, and few-shot configurations.

3.1 MODEL ARCHITECTURE

We focus on Qwen 3.0 (Yang et al., 2025), a current decoder-only transformer architecture providing flexibility for various prompting strategies and generation tasks. We evaluate two model sizes: Qwen 3.0-0.6B and Qwen 3.0-1.7B, enabling analysis of performance scaling with model capacity.

3.2 TRAINING METHODOLOGIES

We evaluate three approaches: (1) zero-shot inference, (2) supervised fine-tuning (SFT) with next-token prediction loss, and (3) GRPO optimizing composite reward functions.

Our GRPO implementation uses ROUGE-L score (95% weight) and length penalty (5% weight). We experimented with various weight combinations and found that the 95%/5% configuration provided the most stable training process and optimal performance across evaluation metrics. Training uses LoRA rank 64, alpha 128 (Hu et al., 2022), learning rates of 1e-6 (GRPO) and 2e-4 (SFT), 3 epochs with cosine scheduling, and 1000/100 warm-up steps respectively.

3.3 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

We evaluate 24 configurations varying model size (0.6B/1.7B), prompting strategy (basic/engineered), few-shot examples (0/2-shot), and training method (None/SFT/GRPO), as shown in Figure 1. Evaluation uses ROUGE-L, BLEU, BERTScore (Zhang et al., 2020a), and F1-RadGraph (Jain et al., 2021) for clinical correctness.

4 RESULTS

We evaluate on MIMIC-III (Johnson et al., 2016) with 79,790 radiology reports. Table 1 shows GRPO consistently outperforms baselines and supervised fine-tuning. The best performance: 1.7B model with prompt engineering, 2-shot examples, and GRPO achieves 32.65 ROUGE-L and 30.28 F1-RadGraph.

Table 1: Performance comparison across experimental configurations

Fine-tuning	Model	Prompting	Few-shot	ROUGE-L	BLEU	BERT	F1-RadGraph
None	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	0	21.24	0.0613	85.54	23.22
SFT	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	0	25.88	0.0966	85.80	25.10
GRPO	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	0	26.65	0.1158	86.57	26.66
None	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	0	21.16	0.0619	85.25	23.42
SFT	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	0	26.52	0.0834	84.70	28.00
GRPO	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	0	26.68	0.1137	86.34	27.39
None	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	2	20.83	0.0780	85.22	18.83
SFT	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	2	24.05	0.0587	84.67	26.94
GRPO	Qwen3-0.6B	Basic	2	29.67	0.1275	86.98	28.22
None	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	2	20.69	0.0694	84.70	21.24
SFT	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	2	27.09	0.0868	85.91	27.48
GRPO	Qwen3-0.6B	Engineered	2	29.82	0.1410	86.94	28.77
None	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	0	21.27	0.0618	85.54	23.23
SFT	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	0	25.02	0.0680	85.18	27.74
GRPO	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	0	27.90	0.1062	86.66	26.86
None	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	0	21.16	0.0619	85.25	23.40
SFT	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	0	25.74	0.0738	85.42	27.50
GRPO	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	0	28.93	0.1235	86.76	27.03
None	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	2	20.94	0.0780	85.21	18.78
SFT	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	2	29.21	0.1075	86.62	29.31
GRPO	Qwen3-1.7B	Basic	2	31.63	0.1456	87.35	29.70
None	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	2	20.69	0.0694	84.70	21.24
SFT	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	2	28.16	0.0938	86.22	28.55
GRPO	Qwen3-1.7B	Engineered	2	32.65	0.1536	87.31	30.28

GRPO shows substantial improvements (0.6B model: 29.82 vs. 21.24 baseline ROUGE-L). SFT often underperforms base models in smaller configurations, suggesting GRPO’s composite reward function provides more effective guidance than next-token prediction loss.

5 CONCLUSION

We presented the first application of GRPO to radiology report summarization, demonstrating consistent improvements over baseline and SFT approaches across 24 configurations. GRPO’s effectiveness depends on model size and prompting strategy interactions, with larger models benefiting most from prompt engineering. GRPO serves as capability amplification (Rajani et al., 2025), while SFT often plateaus in smaller models.

Limitations include GRPO’s reliance on base model capabilities, sensitivity to hyperparameters, computational overhead, and focus on automatic rather than clinical metrics. Future work should explore robust reward design, GRPO-SFT hybrid approaches, and clinical validation studies.

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A APPENDIX

A.1 QWEN 3.0 MODEL ARCHITECTURE

Qwen 3.0 (Yang et al., 2025) represents a current decoder-only transformer architecture developed by Alibaba Cloud. We selected Qwen 3.0 for several key reasons that align with our research objectives:

Model Variants and Scale: The Qwen 3.0 family offers extensive model variants across different scales and specializations, providing flexibility for various deployment scenarios. The family includes base models ranging from 0.6B to 235B parameters, instruction-tuned variants optimized for following human instructions, and thinking models designed for complex reasoning tasks. Additionally, specialized base models with different training configurations are available to suit specific use cases.

Scale and Efficiency: For our study, we focused on the smaller base models (Qwen3-0.6B and Qwen3-1.7B) to enable systematic analysis of performance scaling effects in medical text summarization while maintaining practical deployment feasibility in resource-constrained healthcare environments. These sizes represent practical deployment scenarios while providing sufficient capacity for complex medical language understanding.

Fine-tuning Compatibility: The architecture’s design supports efficient parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods like LoRA, enabling practical deployment in medical settings where computational resources may be limited. The model’s attention mechanisms and tokenization approach are well-suited for processing structured medical reports with their characteristic terminology and formatting.

Reproducibility and Accessibility: Qwen 3.0 models are publicly available with comprehensive documentation, supporting reproducible research in medical artificial intelligence applications. The model’s open availability enables broader adoption and validation of our findings across different healthcare institutions.

A.2 GROUP RELATIVE POLICY OPTIMIZATION (GRPO)

Group Relative Policy Optimization (GRPO) (Shao et al., 2024) represents an advancement in reinforcement learning-based fine-tuning that addresses key limitations of traditional RLHF approaches while enabling fine-grained control over training objectives.

Theoretical Foundation: GRPO builds upon policy gradient methods but introduces group-based relative comparisons rather than absolute reward maximization. The algorithm optimizes policies by comparing outputs within groups of generated samples, reducing variance and improving training stability compared to standard RLHF approaches.

Composite Reward Functions: Unlike traditional supervised fine-tuning that optimizes single objectives (typically next-token prediction loss), GRPO enables optimization of weighted combinations of multiple reward functions. In our implementation, we combine ROUGE-L scores (95% weight) for syntactic similarity with length penalties (5% weight) to encourage appropriate summary lengths.

Training Stability: GRPO addresses common RLHF challenges including reward hacking, training instability, and mode collapse through its group-relative comparison mechanism. By comparing generated outputs within batches rather than against absolute reward thresholds, the method maintains more stable gradients throughout training.

Computational Efficiency: The algorithm requires fewer computational resources than full RLHF implementations while achieving comparable or superior performance. This efficiency stems from the simplified reward computation and reduced need for separate reward model training, making it particularly suitable for medical applications where computational resources may be constrained.

Medical Domain Applicability: GRPO’s ability to incorporate domain-specific reward functions makes it particularly valuable for medical text generation tasks. The method can simultaneously optimize for syntactic quality (ROUGE scores) and semantic correctness (clinical accuracy metrics), addressing the multi-faceted nature of medical text quality assessment.

A.3 EVALUATION METRICS

Our comprehensive evaluation employs four complementary metrics that capture different aspects of summarization quality, providing a holistic assessment of model performance across syntactic, semantic, and clinical dimensions.

ROUGE-L (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation - Longest Common Subsequence): ROUGE-L measures the longest common subsequence between generated and reference summaries, capturing structural similarity and word order preservation. This metric is particularly relevant for medical summarization where maintaining clinical terminology order and relationships is crucial for accuracy. ROUGE-L scores range from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating better alignment with reference summaries.

BLEU (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy): BLEU evaluates n-gram precision between generated and reference texts, emphasizing exact phrase matching. While originally designed for machine translation, BLEU provides valuable insights into lexical overlap and phrase-level accuracy in medical summarization. The metric uses geometric mean of n-gram precisions (typically n=1 to 4) with brevity penalty to discourage overly short outputs.

BERTScore: BERTScore (Zhang et al., 2020a) leverages contextual embeddings from pre-trained BERT models to compute semantic similarity between generated and reference summaries. Unlike surface-level metrics, BERTScore captures semantic equivalence even when exact wording differs, making it particularly valuable for medical texts where multiple valid phrasings may convey identical clinical meaning. The metric computes cosine similarity between contextualized token embeddings, providing scores that correlate well with human judgments of semantic similarity.

F1-RadGraph: F1-RadGraph (Jain et al., 2021) represents a specialized clinical evaluation metric designed specifically for radiology report assessment. The metric extracts clinical entities and relationships from both generated and reference summaries using RadGraph, a clinical information extraction system trained on radiology reports. F1-RadGraph then computes F1 scores based on the overlap of extracted clinical facts, providing direct measurement of clinical accuracy and factual correctness. This metric is crucial for medical applications where semantic accuracy directly impacts clinical decision-making.

Metric Complementarity: These four metrics provide complementary perspectives on summarization quality. ROUGE-L and BLEU capture surface-level similarity and structural alignment, BERTScore evaluates semantic similarity, and F1-RadGraph assesses clinical factual accuracy. This multi-dimensional evaluation approach ensures comprehensive assessment of model performance across the various quality aspects relevant to medical text summarization.

Clinical Relevance: The combination of automatic metrics provides practical evaluation suitable for large-scale experiments while maintaining clinical relevance. F1-RadGraph specifically addresses the medical domain’s unique requirements for factual accuracy, while the other metrics ensure general text quality standards are maintained.